

Analysis and Research of Two-Level Scheduling Profile for Open Real-Time System

Yongxian Jin, Jingzhou Huang

Abstract—In an open real-time system environment, the coexistence of different kinds of real-time and non real-time applications makes the system scheduling mechanism face new requirements and challenges. One two-level scheduling scheme of the open real-time systems is introduced, and points out that hard and soft real-time applications are scheduled non-distinctively as the same type real-time applications, the Quality of Service (QoS) cannot be guaranteed. It has two flaws: The first, it can not differentiate scheduling priorities of hard and soft real-time applications, that is to say, it neglects characteristic differences between hard real-time applications and soft ones, so it does not suit a more complex real-time environment. The second, the worst case execution time of soft real-time applications cannot be predicted exactly, so it is not worth while to cost much spending in order to assure all soft real-time applications not to miss their deadlines, and doing that may cause resource wasting. In order to solve this problem, a novel two-level real-time scheduling mechanism (including scheduling profile and scheduling algorithm) which adds the process of dealing with soft real-time applications is proposed.

Finally, we verify real-time scheduling mechanism from two aspects of theory and experiment. The results indicate that our scheduling mechanism can achieve the following objectives. (1) It can reflect the difference of priority when scheduling hard and soft real-time applications. (2) It can ensure schedulability of hard real-time applications, that is, their rate of missing deadline is 0. (3) The overall rate of missing deadline of soft real-time applications can be less than 1. (4) The deadline of a non-real-time application is not set, whereas the scheduling algorithm that server S_0 uses can avoid the “starvation” of jobs and increase QOS. By doing that, our scheduling mechanism is more compatible with different types of applications and it will be applied more widely.

Keywords—Hard real-time; two-level scheduling profile; open real-time system; non-distinctive schedule; soft real-time.

I. INTRODUCTION

WITH the development of real-time systems, the application of open real-time system, in which hard, soft and non real-time applications are included, is getting more and more widespread. This brings new demands and challenges to the scheduling. So those scheduling approaches, which are proposed for closed real-time system and suitable for simplex scope, have already not meet people’s demands. Therefore the concept “open real-time system” (ORTS) has been proposed in recent years. The ORTS’s uppermost characteristic is: when the system is running, all the real-time or non real-time applications that are developed and validated independently can be configured dynamically and join in the system, then they will concurrent with original applications;

and at the time the system is expanded dynamically, the global schedulability analysis is not needed [1].

After studying scheduling profile [1], this paper points out the scheme that schedules hard and soft real-time applications by regarding them as the same ones cannot assure QoS, then an improved scheme is put forward. The improved scheme adds the function of dealing with soft real-time applications, so the problem that schedules hard and soft real-time applications nondistinctively is solved. Meanwhile we have taken account of influences to schedulability brought by non-preemptable sections (NPS). By doing that, our scheduling mechanism is more compatible with different types of applications and it will be applied more widely. The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section II describes related works. In section III, we analyze the limitations of two-level scheduling profile. Section IV presents a novel scheduling profile and scheduling algorithm. Section V and VI give the schedulability analysis and simulation results. We conclude with a short summary and extensions on future work in Section VII.

II. RELATED WORKS

At present, scheduling profile of ORTS include two kinds: the first is the method integrating a variety of scheduling algorithms based on servers within the hierarchical scheduling framework [1]. It is one of the bandwidth reservation algorithms using CUS (constant utilization server) and TBS (total bandwidth server). The two-level scheduling profile is established based on that. It focuses on individualized task scheduling to the application system; the second is the method syncretizing a variety of scheduling algorithms within a unified architecture [2]. It employs a unified system-scheduling model which contains some different scheduling strategies. It permits to configure multiple scheduling strategies in a unified structure, but the system can use only one strategy when running. On the basis of the two kinds of scheduling profile, researchers have brought forward lots of scheduling algorithms for kinds of scheduling objects existing simultaneously in an ORTS.

Generalized Processor Sharing (GPS) algorithm [3] idealizes real-time applications to be a work-flow whose granularity can be subdivided infinitely, and then each real-time task will be allocated certain CPU bandwidth according to its demand. EGPS algorithm [4] inherits the thought in [3]. Constant Bandwidth Server (CBS) [5,6] and Hierarchical CBS (H-CBS) algorithm [7] focuses on the problem of providing efficient run-time support to multimedia applications in a real-time system, where different types of tasks can coexist. The bandwidth

Yong-xian JIN is with College of Mathematics, Physics and Information Science, Zhejiang Normal University, China (E-mail: jyx@zjnu.cn)

reservation mechanism allows real-time tasks to execute in a dynamic environment under a temporal protection mechanism, so that each task will never exceed a predefined bandwidth, independently of its actual request. Earliest Deadline as Late as possible-Red Tasks Only (EDL-RTO) and Blue When Possible (EDL-BWP) [8] are two on-line algorithms, and the objective is to minimize the average response time of soft aperiodic request, while ensuring that the QoS (Quality of Service) of periodic tasks will never be less than a specified bound. Reference [9] presents the non-preemptive Group-EDF algorithm for soft multimedia-application systems. The experiment suggests this algorithm is more efficient in executing soft multimedia applications. Reference [10] focuses on scheduling soft real-time applications of the multiprocessor platform. It points out that compared with partitioned EDF, global EDF can get a higher system utilization. Processor Sharing with Earliest Deadlines First (PShED) algorithm [11] provides independence among scheduling tasks. Rigorously Proportional Dispatching Server (RPDS) algorithm [12] establishes a new hierarchical scheduling framework, and it schedules types of tasks using time chip as the basic unit. Open Adaptive Real-Time Scheduling (OARTS) framework [13], which imports auto control ideas into ORTS scheduling, can adjust real-time priorities of tasks depending on local resources. However, it do not think about characteristics of tasks such as NPS, global resources etc. And they increase burden of the system because of a mass of computing. Reference [14] presents Two-Dimensional Priority Real-Time Scheduling (TDPRTS), and the system allocates different priorities and corresponding bandwidth for different algorithms, but the bandwidth can not be adjusted dynamically. The mechanism is not agile enough so that it is difficult to make full use of system resources. Reference [15] presents a multiprocessor scheduling framework for integrating hard and soft and best-effort (non real-time) tasks. It ensures that hard real-time deadlines are met and that of soft ones are less than a bound.

Research above does not synthetically think about the type of tasks (periodic or aperiodic), the characteristic of tasks (if they contain NPS, if they require global resources) and so on. By contrast, the two-level scheduling profile [1] has its own advantage. The reason is that it admits real-time and non real-time applications and tasks with different characteristics, and it can schedule real-time and non real-time applications in a complex open real-time environment.

III. ANALYSIS OF THE TWO-LEVEL SCHEDULING PROFILE

A. Related Concepts

Definition 1 Open Real-Time System: Non-relevant real-time applications and non-real time applications may be developed and validated independently, and global schedulability analysis is not necessary when the system is extended dynamically [1].

Definition 2 Task: Software entity that can accomplish some function. It is a basic unit of real-time scheduling. An execution during the task's lifetime is called a job of this task. Application is defined by a set consists of multiple tasks.

Definition 3 Server: In this paper it represents a special task established by the system scheduling mechanism. It provides service for scheduling objects [16]. There is more than one server in system and each server is equivalent to a slow processor.

Definition 4 Server Speed: Assume that the speed of system processor is 1. Consider a server as a virtual processor, and then the speed ratio of virtual processor and the system processor is server speed. The server speed of S_k is: $\sigma_k < 1$.

Definition 5 Application Event: It means an action occurred inside the application at some point. In order to ensure schedulability, the server scheduler must keep track of moments application events take place. An event of A_k refers to one of the following: (1) a job in A_k is released or completes; (2) a job in A_k requests for or releases a global resource; (3) a job in A_k enters or leaves a NPS.

B. Analysis for Two-level Scheduling Profile

Fig.1 shows the hierarchical (or called two-level) scheduling framework [1].

Fig. 1 Two-level scheduling architecture

The workload of the processor consists of a variable number N of real-time applications, called A_1, A_2, \dots, A_N , together with non-real-time applications. All non-real time applications are executed by a server S_0 , while each real-time application is executed by a server S_k ($k \geq 1$). The S_0, S_1, \dots, S_N are at the upper level. Each server S_k has a

ready queue containing ready jobs of the real-time application A_k , and ready queue of the server S_0 contains ready jobs of all the non-real-time applications. The server S_0 uses a time-sharing algorithm to schedule ready jobs of all non-real-time applications [17]. At the OS level, the scheduler provided by the operating system, which we call OS scheduler, maintains all the servers in the system. It replenishes the server budget and sets the server deadline for every server according to the characteristics of the applications. A server is ready when its budget is nonzero and its ready queue is not empty. The OS scheduler also has a ready queue, which contains all the ready servers. It schedules all the ready servers according to the EDF algorithm. The hierarchical scheduling scheme, which is based on two kinds of servers CUS (Constant Utilization Server) and TBS (Total Bandwidth Server), is one kind of server scheduling strategies. Server S_i may be CUS or TBS, and it must participate in the system scheduling with deadline. The difference of CUS and TBS is following:

Assume that S_i is a CUS. If its deadline is $d_{i,k}$ at time t , $d_{i,k}$ is calculated as follows:

$$d_{i,k} = \max\{t, d_{i,k-1}\} + e_{i,k} / \sigma_{i,k} \quad (1)$$

Here $\sigma_{i,k}$ denotes the server speed of S_i , and $e_{i,k}$ denotes the remaining WCET (worst case execution time). Server S_i replenishes its budget at time $\max\{t, d_{i,k-1}\}$, and the budget value is $e_{i,k}$. The deadline setting of TBS is the same as CUS, and the difference between them is replenishment time. Suppose job $J_{i,k}$ is released at time t : if $t \geq d_{i,k-1}$, they are the same; if $t < d_{i,k-1}$, TBS can replenish its budget as soon as the job $J_{i,k-1}$ is finished, while CUS has to wait till to time $d_{i,k-1}$ [16].

Scheduling framework mentioned above can manage real-time applications and non-real-time applications. About scheduling non-real-time applications, we have already discussed in detail in [18]. About real-time applications scheduling, the original framework has some characteristics as below:

(1) Each real-time application has its own scheduling algorithm and server. Each server is allocated certain bandwidth and it must maintain the current application's ready queue and take part in scheduling in OS level.

(2) There are no restrictions on the type of tasks contained in real-time applications. Periodic tasks, aperiodic tasks and sporadic tasks are all allowed.

(3) It does not strictly limit tasks' characteristics in a real-time application: 1) tasks may preempt each other. 2) Tasks may request for global resources. 3) Tasks may have NPS. For those tasks that are nonpredictable or request for global resources or have nonpreemptable sections, we must prepare sufficient bandwidth in advance to ensure their schedulability.

(4) When a real-time application enters the system, global schedulability analysis is not necessary, but the application

has to pass the acceptance test. Only applications that meet some conditions can be accepted.

From the four points we know that the original framework can manage multi-types real-time tasks with a variety of characteristics and ensure their schedulability. However, it does not consider the differences between hard and soft real-time applications when scheduling them, that is to say, it applies only to hard real-time applications. If T_i is a hard real-time task, e_i represents its job's WCET without being interrupted. If T_i is a soft real-time task, e_i is a statistical or estimated value [12]. So for a soft real-time application which is made up of soft real-time tasks, the server speed and execution time it demands are estimated values when executing. If we use the original framework to execute a soft real-time application and its actual execution time is longer than the estimated value, we will not ensure the schedulability of system. In addition, there is another difference between hard and soft real-time applications. A hard real-time application must not miss its deadline; otherwise it will result in a disaster. A soft real-time application has an estimated deadline, even though some miss their deadlines, it will not have a significant loss. However, in practice, we should try out best to lower the rate of missing deadline to increase QOS (Quality of Service).

For that reason, we attempt to modify the part of scheduling real-time applications. It is hoped to present a new scheduling mechanism to achieve the following objectives:

(1) It should reflect the difference of priority when scheduling hard and soft real-time applications.

(2) It should ensure schedulability of hard real-time applications, that is, their rate of missing deadline is still 0.

(3) The overall rate of missing deadline of soft real-time applications should be less than 1.

(4) The deadline of a non-real-time application is not set, whereas the scheduling algorithm server S_0 uses should try to avoid the "starvation" of jobs.

IV. A NOVEL SCHEDULING PROFILE AND SCHEDULING ALGORITHM

To achieve our objectives, a novel scheduling profile is as follows (shown in Fig. 2). The server ready queue of OS level is divided into three parts: hard, soft and non-real-time respectively. Server schedulers of hard and soft real-time applications use the EDF algorithm, and that of non-real-time applications uses a time-sharing algorithm.

The discussion will be carried on the premise of the following conditions:

(1) Tasks in hard and soft real-time applications are all periodic, and they are scheduled by preemptive algorithms.

(2) All applications are predictable. Periods of tasks in applications are equal to their relative deadlines, and a job is always released at the beginning of the period.

(3) Hard and soft real-time applications can include NPS or use global resources, but if a non-real-time application includes NPS or use global resources, it will be scheduled as a soft real-time application.

(4) In this paper a task is the basic scheduling unit. An application's schedulability is proved through the schedulability of tasks it includes, that is, if tasks in an application are all schedulable, the application is schedulable.

Fig. 2 Novel two-level scheduling profile

The general idea of our new scheduling algorithm is that different priorities are given three server ready queues which respectively have hard real-time jobs, soft real-time jobs and non-real-time jobs. In the system if there are hard real-time jobs which are ready, they will be executed firstly. When the server ready queue of hard real-time jobs is empty, soft real-time jobs will be executed. When the two ready queues above are empty, non-real-time jobs will be executed. When a job with lower priority is being executed, if a job with higher priority becomes ready, it will preempt the former one immediately. In the following text, some parameters are:

U_0 : The fixed bandwidth allocated to non-real-time applications when the system starts. It does not change till the system terminates.

U_h : The total CPU utilization ratio of all hard real-time applications in the system.

U_s : The total CPU utilization ratio of all soft real-time applications in the system.

U_t : The total CPU utilization ratio of system, namely the total bandwidth already allocated, it meets the equation:

$$U_t = U_h + U_s + U_0 \quad (2)$$

$$\text{and } U_t \leq 1 \quad (3)$$

B_j : The maximum execution time of the NPS of all jobs other than J_j , that is, B_j is the maximum blocking time the job J_j can suffer due to the non-preemptivity of other jobs.

An application must accept the acceptance test before entrance. If a non-real-time application contains NPS or needs global resources, it will be scheduled as a soft real-time application. Otherwise it will directly enter the scheduling

queue of non-real-time applications. When a new application A_k requests for admittance, it provides the following information in its admission request:

- The scheduling algorithm \sum_k by A_k .
- The speed σ_k of the slow processor on which A_k is schedulable.
- The maximum length L_k of all NPS or critical sections guarding global resources used by A_k .
- The shortest relative deadline δ_j of all jobs in A_k if A_k is a priority driven application, or the shortest length δ_j between any two consecutive events of A_k if A_k is a time-driven application.

Then the system will respond to that as follows:

- Find the type of the server for A_k , TBS or CUS (in this paper it must be TBS).
- Allocate the bandwidth U_k for A_k (here, application are predictable, so $U_k = \sigma_k$).
- If $U_t + U_k + \max_{1 \leq j \leq N} \{B_j / \delta_j\} > 1$ (N is total number of applications in the system including A_k), reject A_k . Else, admit A_k , and do following work: create a TBS S_k with server speed U_k for A_k ; set server budget and server deadline to zero and increase U_t by U_k [1].

At application level, if an application releases a new job, the job will be inserted to the ready queue in order according to the algorithm used by the scheduler. At OS level, the system must check ready queues of all real-time applications continuously. When a job is ready, the system replenishes the corresponding server's budget and sets its deadline. Then the server will join the corresponding server ready queue. The server scheduling algorithm is:

Step1: Check whether the hard real-time server ready queue is empty, if empty, go to Step2; else, schedule the first server in the ready queue and execute the job. When the execution completes, move the server out of the server ready queue, go to Step1.

Step2: Check whether the soft real-time server ready queue is empty, if empty, go to Step3; else, schedule the first server in the ready queue and execute the job. When the execution completes, move the server out of the server ready queue, go to Step1.

Step3: Check whether the non-real-time server is ready, if it is ready, execute jobs till the moment the next application event occurs; go to Step1.

IV. SCHEDULABILITY PROOF

Next we will verify whether our two-level scheduling profile can achieve the anticipatory objects:

(1) Through the description of the algorithm, we know that hard real-time jobs always have priority over soft real-time and non real-time jobs, and hard real-time jobs are blocked only happens when soft ones are in their NPS or holding

global resources. If that happens, can hard real-time jobs complete before their deadlines? In other words, will soft real-time jobs affect the schedulability of hard ones or not? It will be proved in (2).

(2) To ensure the rate of missing deadline of hard real-time application is 0, we need make all jobs released by this application must complete before their deadlines.

Here, three points need to be proved: 1) if real-time applications do not have NPS or request for global resources, hard real-time applications are schedulable. 2) If a hard real-time application has NPS or requests for global resources, it will not affect other hard real-time applications' schedulability. 3) If a soft real-time application has NPS or requests for global resources, it will not affect hard real-time applications' schedulability. They will be proved by the following three theorems.

Theorem 1: if the system uses the EDF algorithm to schedule the server ready queue of hard real-time applications and if real-time applications do not have NPS or use global resources, hard real-time applications are schedulable.

Proof: (i) Real-time applications include hard and soft ones. If they do not have NPS or use global resources, according to our algorithm, soft real-time jobs will never block hard ones. Thus, soft real-time applications do not affect the schedulability of hard ones. (ii) Liu CL *et al.*[19] have proved that in a task set which includes many hard real-time tasks, if and only if the CPU utilization ratio of all tasks is not more than 1, the task set is schedulable with the EDF algorithm. And if a task set is schedulable with other algorithms, it is also schedulable with the EDF algorithm. In this sense, the EDF algorithm is optimal. In this paper, the total CPU utilization ratio of all hard real-time applications $U_h \leq U_i \leq 1$, then it meets the necessary and sufficient condition mentioned above, so that hard real-time applications are schedulable.

Theorem 2: if the system uses the EDF algorithm to schedule the server ready queue of hard real-time applications, then NPS contained in a hard real-time application or global resources required by it will not affect the schedulability of the other hard ones.

Proof: We prove the theorem by contradiction. Suppose NPS in the task T_1 has affected the schedulability of the task T_2 . The two jobs they release are respectively J_1 and J_2 . The release time of the two jobs are r_1 and r_2 , and deadlines are d_1 and d_2 . The time interval of NPS in J_1 is $[t_0, t_1]$. The execution time of J_2 is e_2 . T_2 's period is p_2 . Let's see Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 An example about NPS and schedulability

1) Because NPS in J_1 has blocked J_2 , there must be $d_2 < d_1$ and $t_0 \leq r_2 < t_1$. t_N denotes the time length

between r_2 and t_1 . That is to say, J_2 has to wait for t_N to be executed after it is released, and J_2 will miss its deadline. Then

$$t_N + e_2 > d_2 - r_2 = p_2 \quad (4)$$

and more,

$$1 < \sigma_2 + t_N / p_2 < U_i + \max_{1 \leq j \leq N} \{B_j / \delta_j\} \quad (5)$$

Apparently it is in contradiction with the permission condition in acceptance test, so we have made a wrong assumption. In other words, even if some hard real-time job is blocked by NPS, it will be schedulable provided that it follows the permission condition.

2) Here there is a more complex case. Suppose the job J_i 's period is p_i and its execution time is e_i . Its release time r_i is after t_0 while its deadline d_i is right before d_2 , and it makes J_2 unschedulable. From 1) we know J_i is schedulable. According to the relationship between p_i and p_2 (respectively the period of J_i and J_2), we will discuss the following two cases:

(i) $p_i \leq p_2$

From the condition above, we get $e_i / p_2 \leq e_i / p_i$. And from Fig. 3, we know that whenever J_i is released, the following inequation (6) is always true.

$$t_N + e_i + e_2 > p_2 \quad (6)$$

So: $1 < t_N / p_2 + e_i / p_2 + \sigma_2 \quad (7)$

Furthermore: $1 \leq t_N / p_2 + e_i / p_i + \sigma_2$
 $= t_N / p_2 + \sigma_i + \sigma_2$
 $< U_i + \max_{1 \leq j \leq N} \{B_j / \delta_j\} \quad (8)$

It is in contradiction with the permission condition. The assumption is wrong.

(ii) $p_i > p_2$

According to the assumption, we have $t_0 < r_i < r_2$, then

$$\begin{aligned} (t_1 - t_0) / p_2 + e_2 / p_2 + e_i / p_i &\geq (t_1 - r_i) / p_2 + e_2 / p_2 + e_i / p_i \\ &\geq (t_1 - r_i) / p_2 + (e_2 + e_i) / p_i \\ &\geq (t_1 - r_i + e_2 + e_i) / p_i \\ &> (t_1 - r_i + d_i - t_1) / p_i \\ &= 1 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

On the other hand,

$$\begin{aligned} (t_1 - t_0) / p_2 + e_2 / p_2 + e_i / p_i &\leq \max_{1 \leq j \leq N} \{B_j / \delta_j\} + \sigma_2 + \sigma_i \\ &< \max_{1 \leq j \leq N} \{B_j / \delta_j\} + U_i \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

So: $1 < (t_1 - t_0) / p_2 + e_2 / p_2 + e_i / p_i$
 $< \max_{1 \leq j \leq N} \{B_j / \delta_j\} + U_i \quad (11)$

That is: $1 < \max_{1 \leq j \leq N} \{B_j / \delta_j\} + U_i \quad (12)$

It is in contradiction with the permission condition. The assumption is wrong.

From (i) and (ii) we know J_i will not affect J_2 's schedulability. Other cases can be proved like that.

1) and 2) tell us that whether directly or indirectly, a hard real-time job which has NPS or use global resources will not affect the schedulability of the other hard ones. So the schedulability of a hard real-time application made up of hard real-time tasks can be ensured.

Theorem 3: if the system uses the EDF algorithm to schedule the server ready queue of hard real-time applications, then NPS contained in a soft real-time application or global resource will not affect the schedulability of hard ones.

Proof: here, $\max_{1 \leq j \leq N} \{B_j/\delta_j\}$ applies to all the hard and soft real-time applications. When a job enters its NPS, regardless of hard one or soft one, its affection to the schedulability of a hard real-time job is all the same. So the proof is the same as that of Theorem 2.

From the three theorems above we see that our scheme and algorithm can ensure hard real-time applications' schedulability.

(3) Next we will validate whether soft real-time applications' total rate of missing deadline is less than 1 in the improved scheme.

If there are no hard real-time applications, soft real-time applications will get the highest priority. Theorem 1 and Theorem 2 show that they are schedulable statistically. Therefore, the existence of hard real-time applications is the reason why the soft ones miss their deadlines. Assume there are m hard real-time tasks and n soft ones, and the lowest common multiple of all tasks' periods is p . If every execution of these n soft real-time tasks has missed its deadline, then according to the algorithm, it is impossible to execute non-real-time tasks within p . That's to say, during the time interval, the total CPU utilization ratio it needs which makes all tasks schedulable is more than 1. However, all tasks are periodic so that the state will not be improved. It contradicts the permission condition. Consequently at least one soft real-time job must complete within p . Then it is concluded that the statistic rate of missing deadline of soft real-time applications is less than 1.

(4) When it starts the system reserves bandwidth U_0 for non-real-time applications. The two-level profile can implement the bandwidth isolation, so within p , non-real-time jobs will execute for $p \times U_0$. It has been discussed in [18] and that approach can avoid "starvation" and increase QOS.

VI. SIMULATION AND ANALYSIS

Following we make a simulation to test the validity of the new scheduling algorithm.

A. Testing Environment

This experiment is performed in a PC with single CPU, and main parameters are:

- (1) CPU: Pentium4 frequency 3.0G Hz;
- (2) Main memory: DDR SDRAM, frequency 400MHz,

- capacity 512M;
- (3) External storage: Western Digital, rev 7200 r/m, capacity 80G;
- (4) Operating system: WINDOWS XP PROFESSIONAL;
- (5) Programming language: JAVA 2, JDK 1.6.0;
- (6) Programming environment: ECLIPSE 3.4.1;
- (7) Drawing tool: MATLAB R2007a.

B. schematic design

In order to highlight the algorithm's performance and eliminate influences from testing environment, scheduling spending and timer error to results, periods of real-time tasks are set in second grade. Tasks' characteristic parameters, such as the number of tasks, if a task contains NPS, the length of NPS, a task is hard one or soft one, the length of a task's period and the bandwidth a task needs, are generated automatically by system. In the process 30 tasks are generated, and each task is executed 10 times, and periods of tasks range from 10s to 60s. The result is counted according to the respective execution number of hard and soft real-time tasks, specifically, the respective DMR (Deadline Miss Ratio) is computed every 30 executions. The testing program is a multithreading one, and it is made up of four threads, which are:

(1) Task generation thread: It is responsible for task generation. When generating tasks, it sets the length of a task, the bandwidth a task needs, WCET, the execution number and determines whether a real-time task is hard or soft. New tasks join the waiting queue. The thread will wait when the waiting queue is full.

(2) Acceptance test thread: This thread examines the task generation queue and performs acceptance test to tasks in the queue. Tasks that meet conditions enter the system, and then they are removed from the queue. When the system can not accept any task in the queue, the thread notifies task generation thread to generate new tasks. After that the thread waits till some task quits from system.

(3) Task execution thread: This thread executes and switches real-time tasks in system according to the algorithm described in 3.3.2. When some task is running, if another task is ready, the system will stop executing the current task, save its context state and put it into the corresponding ready queue in order. Then the system will schedule real-time tasks in the ready queue over again (only one exception: if the current real-time task is a hard one and a soft one is ready, the execution will not be interrupted). If the current task is located in its NPS, the system will not act until the task leaves its NPS.

(4) Waiting queue of system tasks maintenance thread: Tasks executed by system are periodic, so after one execution a task has to wait till the next period begins, and at this moment it will be inserted into the waiting queue of system tasks. The system examines tasks in the queue. When some task's period begins, it will be put into the corresponding ready queue.

C. Results Analysis

We make experiments for different load efficiency, and hard and soft real-time tasks execute more than 250 times respectively.

(1) Light load: As is shown in Fig.4, we can see DMR of all hard and soft real-time tasks stay 0 all the time (the two curved shapes coincide with X axis), in other words, there are no tasks that miss their deadlines. The result is in accord with our supposition.

(2) Middle load: Through experiment we know all tasks meet their deadlines. The algorithm we use has the effects as good as that on light load condition. So we get the graph just the same as Fig. 4.

(3) Full load: According to simulation result (shown in Fig. 5), no hard real-time tasks miss their deadlines (the curved shape coincides with X axis), while the maximum of missing deadline rate of soft real-time tasks is smaller than 7%. The result testifies theorems and indicates our scheduling algorithm can achieve the anticipatory objects. In addition, perhaps soft real-time tasks can not complete before their deadlines, but statistically the system provides better

concurrency for them. The system can accept more soft real-time tasks and execute them concurrently if only the NPS contained in them do not affect the schedulability of hard ones. Thus the system can stay full load evermore and make full use of resources.

(4) Over load: The system does not deny any task, it means the load may vary in a big range. Therefore, it is not proper to display all results in a graph, but we can analyze them. When U_h is bigger than 1, CPU will execute hard real-time tasks all the time, while soft real-time tasks will not be executed. This is not an extreme situation. Now QOS of soft real-time tasks is 0, and we can not conclude accurately how many hard real-time tasks will miss their deadlines, but some of them will have to. The framework and corresponding algorithm is not suitable for the over load condition.

Fig. 4 Comparison of DMR of hard and soft real-time tasks (light and middle load)

Fig. 5 Comparison of DMR of hard and soft real-time tasks (full load)

VII. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This paper focuses on the two-level scheduling profile of ORTS and points out the limitation that the profile only suits a hard real-time environment, and then we present an improved scheduling approach which adds the process of dealing with soft real-time applications. The improved approach solves the problem that schedules hard and soft real-time applications nondistinctively, and it can be applied in a more complex environment. Through proof and simulation, we can see the improved approach can achieve the prospective objectives.

It should be pointed that in more complex environments, an application is not predictable or it includes sporadic tasks, this paper does not discuss. Those problems need to be solved in the future.

REFERENCES

- [1] Z.Deng, J.W.S. Liu. Scheduling Real-Time Applications in an Open Environment. In: Proc. of the 18th IEEE Real-Time Systems Symposium. IEEE Computer Society, 1997, pp.308-319.
- [2] Y.C. Wang, K.J. Lin. Implementing a General Real-Time Scheduling Framework in the RED-Linux Real-Time Kernel. In: Proc. of the 20th IEEE Real-Time Systems Symposium. IEEE Computer Society, 1999, pp. 246-255.
- [3] A.K. Parekh. A generalized processor sharing approach to flow control in integrated services networks [Ph.D. Thesis]. Massachusetts Institute of Technology, 1992.
- [4] T.W. Kuo, W.R. Yang, K.J. Lin. EGPS: a class of real-time scheduling algorithms based on processor sharing. In: Proc. of the 10th Euromicro Workshop on Real Time Systems. IEEE Computer Society, 1998, pp.27-34.
- [5] L.Abeni, G.Buttazzo. Integrating Multimedia Applications in Hard Real-Time Systems. In: Proc. of the 19th IEEE Real-Time Systems Symposium(RTSS'98). IEEE Computer Society, 1998, pp. 4-13.
- [6] L.Abeni, G.Buttazzo. Resource Reservation in Dynamic Real-Time Systems. Real-Time Systems, 2004, 27: pp.123-167.
- [7] G.Lipari, S.Baruah. A Hierarchical Extension to the Constant Bandwidth Server Framework. In: Proc. of the 7th IEEE Real Time Technology and Applications Symposium. IEEE Computer Society, 2001, pp. 26-35.
- [8] A. Marchand, M. Silly-Chetto. Dynamic Real-time Scheduling of Firm Periodic Tasks with Hard and Soft Aperiodic Tasks. Real-Time Systems, 2006, 32(1-2): pp.21-47.
- [9] W.Li, K.Kavi, R.Akl. A non-preemptive scheduling algorithm for soft real-time systems. Computers and Electrical Engineering, 2007, 33(1): pp.12-29.
- [10] U.C. Devi, J.H. Anderson. Tardiness bounds under global EDF scheduling on a multiprocessor. Real-Time System, 2008, 38(2): pp.133-189.
- [11] G.Lipai, J.Carpenter, S.Baruah. A Framework for Achieving Inter-Application Isolation in Multiprogrammed Hard Real-Time Environments. In: Proc. of the 21st IEEE Real-Time Systems Symposium. IEEE Computer Society, 2000, pp. 217-226.
- [12] Y.C. Gong, L.G. Wang, *et al.* A Hybrid Real-Time Scheduling Algorithm Based on Rigorously Proportional Dispatching of Serving. Journal of Software, 2006, 17(3): pp. 611-619. (in Chinese)
- [13] X.Y. Huai, Y.Zou, M.S. Li. An Open Adaptive Scheduling Algorithm for Open Hybrid Real-Time Systems. Journal of Software, 2004, 15(4): pp. 487-496. (in Chinese)
- [14] P.L. Tan, H. Jin, M.H. Zhang. Two-Dimensional Priority Real-Time Scheduling for Open Systems. Acta Electronica Sinica, 2006, 34(1): pp. 1773-1777. (in Chinese)
- [15] B.B. Brandenburg, J.H. Anderson. Integrating Hard/Soft Real-Time Tasks and Best-Effort Jobs on Multiprocessors. In: Proceedings of the 19th Euromicro Conference on Real-Time Systems. IEEE Computer Society, 2007, pp. 61-70.
- [16] Y.Zou, M.S. Li, Q.Wang. Analysis for Scheduling Theory and Approach of Open Real-Time System. Journal of Software, 2003, 14(1): pp. 83-90. (in Chinese)
- [17] Z.Deng, J.W.S. Liu, J.Sun. A Scheme for Scheduling Hard-Real-Time Applications in Open Environment. In: Proc. of the 9th Euromicro Workshop on Real-Time Systems. IEEE Computer Society Press, 1997, pp.191-199.
- [18] Y.X. Jin, J.Z. Huang, J.G. Wang. Scheduling for Non-Real Time Applications of ORTS Based on Two-Level Scheduling Scheme. To appear in: International Journal of Computer Theory and Engineering, 2009, 1(2): pp.170-180.
- [19] C.L. Liu, J.W. Layland. Scheduling Algorithms for Multiprogramming in a Hard Real-Time Environment. Journal of the ACM, 1973, 20(11): pp. 46-61.